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A MODEL FOR ANALYZING THE BARRIERS OF IMPLEMENTING BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE (BI) IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY OF IRAN, A MIXED METHOD APPROACH

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Abstract:

In competitive world, as information technology progresses, organizations are seeking to acquire competitive advantage in global market to survive. One of information technology areas which have been more considered by managers is business intelligence. BI Implementation and using its benefits require the identification of all the factors that prevent of utilizing it desirably. Considering the importance of tourism industry in the countries economy and the impact of BI in organization working in this industry, the study aimed to identify and prioritize BI Barriers in Iran tourism industry. In this research, Barriers on BI implementation and utilization in Iran tourism industry have been performed using a mixed or combination methodology in both qualitative and quantitative measurement. In the qualitative part the grounded theory method and in qualitative section descriptive survey has been used. According to the results, the eleven obstacles based on its priority are as follow respectively: data barriers, managerial barriers, cultural barriers, lack of awareness and education, barriers related to human force, legal and political obstacles, lack of confidence and trust in knowledge transfer, organizational barriers, lack of systems integrity, obstacles related to funding of BI plans and barriers related to infrastructure. The results can facilitate utilizing and implementing of BI in Iran tourist industry.

Keyword(s): BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE, BARRIERS TO USING BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE, TOURISM INDUSTRY